
EDUCATION OF THE YOUNG GENERATION - IMPROVING MORAL QUALITIES IN THE PROCESS OF EDUCATION

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KEYWORDS

Science, education, ethics, means of education, oriental ethics, healthy generation, knowledge, moral qualities

ABSTRACT

The article describes the method of education, the essence of education, the importance of educating poverty, patriotism, high spiritual and moral views, and forming ideological and spiritual immunity in them.

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YOSH AVLOGA TA'LIM – TARBIYA BERISH JARAUONIDA AHLOQIY FAZILATLARNI YUKSALTIRISH

KALIT SO'ZLAR:

Fan, ta'lim, ahloq, tarbiya vositalari, sharqona ahloq, sog'lom avlod, ilm-ma'rifat, ahloqiy fazilatlar

ANNOTATSIYA

Maqolada tarbiya metodi, tarbiya mohiyati, faqirlik, vatanparvarlik tuyg'ularini, yuksak ma'naviy-axloqiy qarashlarni tarbiyalashning, ularda mafkuraviy-ma'naviy immunitetni shakllantirishning dolzarbligi ifodalangan.

Yoshlar tarbiyasi, ularni ilmi va har tomonlama etuk qilib voyaga etkazish barcha zamonlarda muhim vazifa hisoblangan. Mutafakkirlarimiz tomonidan yozib qoldirilgan bunday nodir asarlar o'sib kelayotgan yosh avlodni salbiy illatlardan asrab, axloqan pok, haqiqiy inson bo'lib etishishlariga undagan. Bugun ma'naviyat va yoshlarning ahloqiy tarbiyasi haqida so'z borar ekan, bu xaqdagi bilimlarimizni takomillashtirish, dunyoqarashimizni kengaytirish hamda yoshlarni ana shu yo'lda birlashtirish, kamol toptirishda milliy g'oya xususida to'xtalish muhimdir. Chunki taraqqiyot va texnika asri deb atalmish XXI asr yoshlari qalbida ma'naviy boylik, komil inson darajasiga erishish, yurt-u xalqqa sadoqat hamda muxabbat tuyg'ularini shakllantrishdek ezgu maqsad yotadi. Faxrlanarli tomoni shundaki, bunday muqaddas tushunchalar yurtimizda amalga oshirilayotgan yangilanish va bunyodkorlik ishlari bilan uyg'unlashib bormoqda. Adabiyotshunos olim Abdurauf Fitrat "Xalqning harakat qilishi, davlatmand bo'lishi, baxtli bo'lib izzat-hurmat topishi, jahongir bo'lishi, zaif bo'lib xorlikka tushishi, faqirlik jomasini kiyib, baxtsizlik yukini tortib e'tibordan qolishi, o'zgalarga tobe va qul, asir bo'lishi bolalikdan o'z ota-onalaridan olgan tarbiyalariga bog'liq. Bolalar axloqiy tarbiyani muhitdan oladilar, boshqacha qilib aytganda, bolalar suvga o'xshaydi, suv idishning shaklini olganidek, bolalar ham muhitning odob-axloqini qabul qiladilar", deydi. Inson ahloqiy fazilatlarini samarasi borasidagi bildirilgan fikrlardan shuni anglash mumkinki, tashqi olamning go'zalligi inson ichki olamining go'zalligi samarasidir-tashqi olamning vayronligi inson ichki olamining xunkligidir. Bu boradagi insonning ezgi fazilatlarini ro'yobga chiqarish borasidagi yosh avlodning ta'lim - tarbiya jarayonlari uzluksizligi amalda keng yo'lga qo'yilganligini ijobiy ishlardan deb baholash mumkin. Ayni paytda yana va yana global ko'lamlarda aynan yoshlar tarbiyasida yechimini kutayotgan muammolar mavjudligini tan olishimiz, e'tirof etishimiz kerak. O'zi va o'zgalarning taqdiriga, kelajagiga befarqlik, shafqatsizlik, ishyoqmaslik, halol mehnatdan bo'yin toblash, axloqsizlik, yengil-yelpi va boshqalar hisobiga kun kechirish, giyohvandlik, o'g'irlik, jinoyatchi guruhlar, ekstremistlar va terroristlar faoliyatida ishtirok etish ham jamiyatning aynan navqiron yoshdagi a'zolarini o'z domiga tortayotgani sir emas. Ilm o'rganish, ma'lumot olish uchun sharoit yaratib berayotgan axborot texnologiyalari, jumladan, Internet ham muammolar

manbaiga aylanib borayotganini ta'kidlash zarur. Navoiy xazratlari o'z misralarida: Ilmni kim vositai joh etar, o'ziniyu xalqni gumroh etar deya ilmni noinsoniy yo'lda ishlatuvchi kimsalar nafaqat o'zini, balki xalqni – boshqalarni ham sarson qilishidan bizni ogoh etadi. Ana shu ma'noda bugungi mafkura poligonlaridagi muxoliflarimizning insoniy jihatlari, ma'rifati va ma'naviyati borasida har qancha bahslashishimiz mumkin-u, biroq ularni yoppasiga "o'qimagan, ilmsiz va omi" deb o'ylasak, qattiq yanglishamiz. Mafkura sohasida bo'shliq degan narsaning o'zi hech qachon bo'lmaydi. Chunki insonning qalbi, miyasi, ongu tafakkuri hech qachon axborot olishdan, fikrlashdan, ta'sirlanishdan to'xtamaydi. Demak, unga doimo ma'naviy oziq kerak. Agar shu oziqni o'zi yashayotgan muhitdan olmasa yoki bu muhit uni qoniqtirmasa, nima bo'lishi ayonki, bunday oziqni u asta-sekin boshqa yoqdan izlaydi. Shunga yo'l bermasligimiz lozim hisoblanadi. Mustaqil yurtimizda yuritilayotgan, ertangi kun egalarini har jihatdan kamolga yetkazish siyosati zamirida ham aynan mana shu hayot haqiqati – bugungi dunyoning dolzarb talablari turibdi. Zero, mustaqil hayotga kirib kelayotgan, kuch-g'ayratga to'la va orzulari bepoyon yoshlarga ayni pallalarda amaliy yordam, to'g'ri yo'l-yo'riq ko'rsatish – o'zining ertangi kuniga, farzandlari taqdiriga befarq bo'lmagan xalqning eng muhim vazifasi, buyuk kelajak uchun bunyod etadigan mustahkam poydevori hisoblanadi. Farzandlarimizning kelajakda komil inson bo'lib yetishishlarida oila va jamiyatda yaxshi tarbiya olishning o'rni beqiyosdir. Ota-ona, ustoz-murabbiylar, rahbar va yoshi kattalar qancha madaniyatli, odobli bo'lsa, shu jamiyat va muhitda o'sayotgan shaxslar ham shunchalik odobli bo'lib yetishadi. Bunday sermas'uliyat ijtimoiy ishni amalga oshirish, ya'ni yoshlarimizning odobli, xushxulqli, vijdoni pok kishilar bo'lib yetishishlari uchun o'z xulq-atvorimiz bilan ularga yaxshi ibrat va namuna bo'lishimiz bugungi kunning dolzarb masalasi hisoblanadi.

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